

BUCKLING BEHAVIOUR OF POLYURETHANE FOAM-FILLED COLD-FORMED STEEL C-SECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Thin-walled cold-formed steel (CFS) structural members tend towards failing before reaching their yield strength due to local and distortional instabilities. Global buckling such as Euler or lateral torsional buckling can also occur, however, global buckling is not a specific failure for CFS members. Local buckling means plate buckling of a slender part of the cross-section. Distortional buckling occurs in open cross-sections such as C-sections, at which the flanges under compression buckle inward and outward. In order to improve the local buckling behaviour CFS members are so far provided with stiffeners, seams or corrugations. Though, these provisions are material consuming, complicate the production process and have only a small impact on distortional buckling prevention.

Filling the cross-section with polyurethane foam has a positive effect on the local and distortional buckling behaviour. The polyurethane liquid components are filled into the cross-section and expand inside the profile. The foam supports the cross-section parts normal to their plane and keeps the cross-section in shape. Finite element (FE) elastic buckling analyses have shown, that the critical elastic local and distortional buckling loads are two to three times higher for foam filled section than for regular sections. This leads to an increase of the members load capacity of up to 50 %, depending on the slenderness. The improvement of the foam is also shown in tests on foam-filled C-section columns. Depending on the cross-section shape, the foam can lead to much higher load capacities of CFS members and hence to a more economical design.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cold-formed steel structural members are commonly installed as load-bearing components. In Europe they are mostly used for secondary structures such as purlins or rafters in order to carry façade or roof elements. Industrial steel storage racks are also a field of application. In other countries like North America, Australia or South Africa even primary structures with up to five stories are built of CFS members.

The thickness of CFS is usually smaller than four millimetres. The cross-sections are shaped either by roll forming, which is the most common fabrication method, or by press braking. The shapes of cross-sections are constant along the members.

In this paper open lipped channel C-sections are analysed. As most CFS structural members, the considered C-sections have slender cross-section parts, therefore local and distortional instabilities are likely to occur. Local buckling means plate buckling of a slender part of the cross-section (Figure 1, mode a). Distortional buckling occurs in open cross-sections such as C-sections, at which the flanges under compression buckle inward and outward (Figure 1, mode b). Global buckling such as Euler (Figure 1, mode c) or lateral torsional buckling can also occur, however, global buckling is not a specific failure for CFS members and is not assessed in this paper.

Figure 1: Examples of elastic critical stress for various buckling modes [2]

To lower the slenderness of CFS members, stiffeners, seams or corrugations can be provided. Related to local buckling these provisions have a good effect but the impact on the distortional buckling behaviour of these improvements is relatively small.

Another possibility to reduce the slenderness (local and distortional) of an open C-section is filling the cross-section with polyurethane foam. The polyurethane liquid components are poured into the cross-section and expand inside the member. Thus, a good cast and bond between the foam and the CFS member due to strong self-adhesive characteristic of the foam is ensured. Before the filling, adhesion promoter can be applied to the steel surface to improve the adhesion between foam and steel.

The foam supports the cross-section parts normal to their plane and keeps the cross-section in shape. Finite element elastic buckling analyses have shown, that the critical elastic local and distortional buckling loads are up to three times higher for foam filled sections than for regular sections. This leads to an increase of load capacity of up to 50 %, depending on the slenderness of the member. The improvement of the foam is also shown in tests on foam filled C-section columns. Depending on the cross-section shape, the foam can lead to much higher load capacities of CFS members and hence to a more economical design.

2 COLD-FORMED STEEL DESIGN

In order to value the improving effect of the foam, a design method for foam-filled CFS members has to be found. In the first step, the Direct Strength Method (DSM) is chosen for the following calculations. Schafer and Peköz present the DSM in [5]. Meanwhile the DSM is established in the North American [1] and Australian Standards [6]. The DSM delivers design equations, which allow a prediction of the ultimate load in dependence of the critical elastic buckling stresses separately for local, distortional and global buckling failure. The ability to predict ultimate strength directly is useful for automated parameter analyses. However, the employment of the DSM in the design of foam-filled CFS members has to be verified in the future. For the design of sandwich panels Misiak and Hassinen [7] provide an approach which is based on design equations for unsupported trapezoidal sheeting in consideration of the reduced slenderness of sandwich panel sheeting. The structural behaviour of polyurethane foam on the face sheets of sandwich panels is very similar to the behaviour of the foam on CFS members, therefore this approach is considered viable at this point.

For structural members without foam, elastic buckling properties can be identified by using the finite strip method. Eigen-buckling analyses for a certain range of half-wavelengths deliver an elastic buckling curve, which contains the critical elastic buckling stresses as depicted in Figure 2. The finite strip analyses can be conducted with open source programs such as CUFSM [9]. With CUFSM the buckling properties can be determined with a short computing time and a minimal modelling effort.

For foam-filled members, instead of a finite strip analysis a finite element calculation is required, because the foam has to be modelled with volume finite elements. With an eigenvalue analysis of the finite element model, the smallest critical buckling stresses for the different buckling modes can be found.

The slendernesses λ_l (local) and λ_d (distortional) are obtained from the critical elastic buckling properties of the member. For a beam this leads to:

$$\lambda_l = (M_{crl} / M_y)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda_d = (M_{crd} / M_y)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

M_y - yield moment

M_{crl} - critical elastic local buckling moment

M_{crd} - critical elastic distortional buckling moment

In Figure 2 the elastic buckling curve is exemplarily drawn for a beam.

Figure 2: Elastic buckling curve derived with CUFSM, [3]

By using the slenderness, reduction factors χ_l , χ_d and χ_e can be predicted with the DSM design curves. The ultimate strength of a member is determined with the minimum of the three reduction factors. For a member under bending moment, reduction factors are given below:

$$\chi_n = \min \{ \chi_l, \chi_d, \chi_e \} \quad (3)$$

with:

$$\chi_l = M_{nl} / M_y \quad (4)$$

$$\chi_d = M_{nd} / M_y \quad (5)$$

$$\chi_e = M_{ne} / M_y \quad (6)$$

M_{nl} - nominal local buckling moment capacity

M_{nd} - nominal distortional buckling moment capacity

M_{ne} - nominal global buckling moment capacity

Figure 3: Local and distortional DSM design curves for a braced beam ($M_{ne} = M_y$) [3]

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Finite element analyses have been conducted with the program RFEM [10] for a selection of C-sections. The critical elastic buckling stresses for the local and distortional buckling modes were derived for both column and beam models. As FE models are necessary for the foam filled members, the analysed members without foam are also analysed with FE analyses.

3.1 Cross sections

The analysed cross-sections are common C-sections. Slender cross-sections are chosen in order to emphasise the improving influence of polyurethane foam. The notations are given in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Cross-section notation C-180-60-22-1.5-F6

The following cross sections were analysed.

Column Analyses

Cross-section	$E_c = G_c$ in N/mm ²
C-180-60-22-1.5-NF	No Foam
C-180-60-22-1.5-F6	6
C-180-60-22-1.5-F10	10
C-180-60-22-2.0-NF	No Foam
C-180-60-22-2.0-F6	6
C-180-60-22-2.0-F10	10

Beam Analyses

Cross-section	$E_c = G_c$ in N/mm ²
B-200-60-14-1.5-NF	No Foam
B-200-60-14-1.5-F6	6
B-200-100-14-1.5-NF	No Foam
B-200-100-14-1.5-F6	6
B-200-100-14-1.5-F10	10

Table 1: Cross-sections analysed with RFEM and DSM

3.2 Modelling

The CFS columns and beams were modelled with the 3D-CAD interface of RFEM. The members out to out dimensions as well as corner radiuses were considered in the model. For the CFS members shell finite elements were used. Polyurethane foam was modelled with volume finite elements. Steel material properties are taken from the RFEM data base according to Eurocode 3 [2]. The foam is simulated as an orthotropic material with a variation of the Young's and shear modulus between 4 N/mm² and 10 N/mm². Simplistically the Young's and shear modulus were set equal to each other in every variation. This is considered valid because the calculations are supposed to show a tendency of the dependence of foam-stiffness on critical elastic buckling stresses of CFS members. The material properties are also considered to be equal in any direction of action. The Poisson's ration of the foam was set to 0.2 for all foam variations as it is recommended by Kurpiela in [8].

The column length was set to 1 m. At both ends of the column model all cross section parts are provided with line supports which function like fixed supports (Figure 5). The column is loaded with axial forces by a 1 unit vertical displacement at the column head.

Figure 5: Column finite element model; support and mesh detail (depicted without foam)

The investigated beam length is 3 m. The beams are modelled simply supported, whereas the rotation about the longitudinal axis is fixed at both ends and at both load application points. The beams are analysed in four point bending, the model is loaded with two 1 unit vertical loads, applied as line loads along a vertical line in the web.

Figure 6: Beam finite element model (depicted without foam)

Figure 7: Beam model - Detail at support (depicted without foam) and Mesh detail of rounded corners

The meshing is generated automatically by RFEM, while the finite element mesh refinements where set for all elements to 1 cm. The rounded corners are modelled with a minimum of two elements.

To add the volume finite elements to the model, all surfaces have to be covered. Because of that the open member parts are provided with Null surfaces.

3.3 FE – Results

The critical elastic buckling stresses for the lowest local and distortional eigenvalues are determined with the RFEM Module RFSTABIL. In the following figures, a few exemplary eigenmodes are depicted. The foam leads to shorter buckling half-wavelengths and thus increases the critical elastic buckling stresses for both local and distortional buckling.

Figure 8: Exemplary eigenmodes of column models

Figure 9: Exemplary eigenmodes of beam models

With the DSM design equations, reduction factors for local and distortional buckling are determined. The following tables show the influence of the foam separately for column and beam models.

	$E_c = G_c$ in N/mm ²	$\sigma_{cr,l}$ in kN/cm ²	$\sigma_{cr,d}$ in kN/cm ²	λ_l $\sqrt{(\sigma_y/\sigma_{cr,l})}$	λ_d $\sqrt{(\sigma_y/\sigma_{cr,d})}$	$\chi_l =$ N_{nl}/N_y	$\chi_d =$ N_{nd}/N_y	Load capacity increase in %
C-180-60-22-1.5-NF		7.9	15.7	2.10	1.49	0.50	0.52	
C-180-60-22-1.5-F6	6	20.1	41.1	1.32	0.92	0.70	0.80	39
C-180-60-22-1.5-F10	10	26.5	56.8	1.15	0.78	0.77	0.89	53
C-180-60-22-2.0-NF		13.9	24.6	1.59	1.19	0.62	0.79	
C-180-60-22-2.0-F6	6	28.1	54.9	1.12	0.80	0.79	0.88	28
C-180-60-22-2.0-F10	10	29.8	66.9	1.08	0.72	0.81	0.93	30

Table 2: FE and DSM results of column models

The bearing capacity of the columns with 1.5 mm thickness is up to 53 % higher for the foam-filled members. For columns with a thickness of 2 mm, the foam leads to an increase of the reduction factors of around 30 % for a foam stiffness of 10 N/mm². The controlling buckling mode for the considered columns is local buckling of the web plate.

	$E_c = G_c$ in N/mm ²	$\sigma_{cr,l}$ in kN/cm ²	$\sigma_{cr,d}$ in kN/cm ²	λ_l $\sqrt{(\sigma_y/\sigma_{cr,l})}$	λ_d $\sqrt{(\sigma_y/\sigma_{cr,d})}$	$\chi_l =$ M_{nl}/M_y	$\chi_d =$ M_{nd}/M_y	Load capacity increase in %
B-200-60-14-1.5-NF		38.3	32.6	0.00	0.00	0.88	0.76	
B-200-60-14-1.5-F6	6	72.6	98.3	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	31
B-200-100-14-1.5-NF		23.8	16.3	1.21	1.47	0.75	0.58	
B-200-100-14-1.5-F6	6	40.8		0.93		0.89	1.00	54
B-200-100-14-1.5-F10	10	49.7		0.84		0.95	1.00	64

Table 3: FE and DSM results of beam models

The investigated beam with a flange width of 60 mm has a reduction factor of $\chi_d = 0.76$ if the member is not filled, while distortional buckling is controlling. Foam with a stiffness of 6 N/mm² allows to utilize the full yield capacity of the member ($\chi = 1,0$).

For a wider flange the capacity of the member without foam is equal 58 % of the yield capacity. Foam filled members have higher reduction factors of 0.89 and 0.95. This means that the ultimate capacity can be increased by up to 64 %. The foam strongly reduces the distortional slenderness. Within the first 50 eigenvalues only local modes could be obtained. The 50th eigenmode has a critical local buckling stress of 95 kN/cm². Thus the critical distortional buckling stress has to be at least 95 kN/cm², which leads to a distortional reduction factor of $\chi_d = 1.0$. The possibility to increase the flange width results in a more economical ratio of moment capacity to material use. Besides that a wider cross section has a higher torsional stiffness and a larger moment of inertia about the weak axis, which leads to an improvement on the lateral torsional buckling behaviour of the member.

Additionally, the influence of polyurethane foam on the bearing capacity is visualised in the following plots.

Figure 10: Theoretical load capacities of foam-filled members according DSM design curves

4 COMPRESSION TESTS

4.1 Test setup and description

Two types of C-sections, C-180-60-22-1.5 and C-180-60-22-2.0, were tested. The sections were selected because they have a high slenderness and thus the positive influence of polyurethane foam can be shown considerably. Six columns were tested under axial compression to the failure. The specimen length was chosen to be 720 mm, which is equal to four times the largest cross-section dimension. The specimen dimensions were measured as depicted in Figure 11. In Table 4 the measured cross-section dimensions are given. Tensile specimens were cut out of not plasticized areas of the tested members without foam. Tensile tests were performed according to DIN EN 10002. The foam properties could not be determined yet. Therefore the foam-filled specimens were named with an "x" instead of the actual Young's modulus. However, the foam is presumed to have a Young's modulus between 6 N/mm² and 10 N/mm².

Figure 11: Cross-section dimension notation [4]

Specimen	H	B1	B2	D1	D2	F1	F2	S1	S2	RB1	RB2	RT1	RT2	t
C-180-60-22-1,5-NF-1	178,3	59,9	60,2	20,9	22,3	89,0°	88,8°	-7,5°	-3,0°	5,5	5	6	6,5	1,45
C-180-60-22-1,5-Fx-1	177,2	59,8	59,6	21,1	23,0	89,5°	92,5°	-8,0°	-4,0°	5,5	5	6	6,5	1,45
C-180-60-22-1,5-Fx-2	178,2	59,9	60,1	21,1	22,6	89,7°	88,8°	-8,0°	-4,0°	5,5	6	6,5	6,5	1,46
C-180-60-22-2.0-NF-1	179,6	60,4	60,5	19,5	22,1	89,7°	89,3°	-5,0°	-2,0°	6	5,5	5	5,5	1,94
C-180-60-22-2.0-Fx-1	179,5	60,4	60,5	19,6	21,7	89,7°	89,3°	-5,0°	-2,0°	5,5	5	5	5,5	1,95
C-180-60-22-2.0-Fx-2	179,3	60,4	60,5	18,5	21,9	90,0°	89,5°	-5,0°	-2,0°	5	5	5	5,5	1,98

Table 4: Specimen cross-section dimensions in mm

The tests were conducted according to EC3-1-3 [2] section A.3.2.1 in displacement control using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) with a capacity of 200 tons. For the selected sections, significant post-buckling reserves are expected. Because of the cross-sections asymmetry, local buckling in the web causes a shift in the neutral axis of the cross-section. This will cause an application of a bending moment, if the load is applied by pinned ends. To avoid that, the tests were performed with rotationally stiff plates at the column top and bottom, thus a uniform stress application is provided during the entire testing procedure. The specimens were milled evenly at both ends in order to prevent local failure at load application. The members were held in place by friction.

A picture of the test setup is given in Figure 12. The load was applied by a hydraulic cylinder. Force was measured by a load cell that is integrated in the UTM. The axial displacement was measured with a draw wire displacement sensor.

Figure 12: Compression test setup

4.2 Test results

In this chapter, results of the first conducted tests are presented. This research project is at its beginning, thus, not all properties especially foam properties have been detected yet. A precise evaluation of the performed experiments and a prediction of nominal strength per DSM is not possible for foam-filled specimens at the time of the editorial deadline for these proceedings.

All tests failed initiated by local buckling modes. Regardless of specimen geometries, local buckling occurred in the web first. A typical elastic buckling behaviour is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Elastic buckling of the web plate, test C-180-60-22-2.0-NF-1

The buckling half-wavelengths were observed to be smaller for the foam-filled members. As expected, the ultimate load could be increased by the polyurethane foam. In Table 5 the ultimate loads of the performed tests are given. Load vs. axial shortening for the test series is plotted in Figure 14.

Specimen	Ultimate load in kN	Load capacity increase in %	Nominal Strength per DSM in kN
C-180-60-22-1.5-NF-1	88.5		82.7
C-180-60-22-1.5-Fx-1	107.0	21.0	
C-180-60-22-1.5-Fx-2	112.2	26.9	
C-180-60-22-2.0-NF-1	152.4		144.6
C-180-60-22-2.0-Fx-1	189.1	24.0	
C-180-60-22-2.0-Fx-2	190.5	25.0	

Table 5: Ultimate loads of the conducted tests

Figure 14: Compression tests - load vs. axial shortening

Ultimate load of the specimens without foam could also be calculated with the DSM as described in chapter 2. Actual dimensions as well as yield stresses of the members were considered. The ultimate loads of the tested columns are slightly higher (up to 7 %) than the nominal strength predicted per DSM, which is considered to be accurate by still being conservative.

Load capacity increases up to 27 % for the foam-filled members with a thickness of 1.5 mm versus the plain member. Foam-filled CFS columns with a thickness of 2 mm have an ultimate load that is up to 25 % higher than members without foam. Assuming to have the same foam properties for all tested members and compared to the results of the finite element analyses, the impact of the foam on the columns with a thickness of 1.5 mm should be much higher (40 % to 50 % instead of 27 %). For the 1.5 mm thick specimens a poor adhesion between the foam and the CFS was observed. Out of plane deflections of the web plate (local buckling) led to a delamination from the foam. In Figure 15 a cut out piece of web of specimen C-180-60-22-1.5-Fx-2 is depicted. The foam could be removed easily by hand without any foam remaining on the metal surface. However, a good adhesion between foam and steel was noticed in test C-180-60-22-2.0-Fx-2.0 as foam failure occurred in between the foam (see Figure 16). Figure 14 shows that the axial stiffness of the foam-filled members is increased by the polyurethane foam. The curves of the foam-filled members with a thickness of 1.5 mm both drop by approx. 10 kN at around 85 kN (C180-60-22-1.5-Fx-1) respectively 110 kN (C180-60-22-1.5-Fx-2). At these points inelastic buckling occurred, but did not lead to an instant global failure.

Figure 15: Cut out piece of web of specimen C-180-60-22-1.5-Fx-2

Figure 16: Failure in between the foam of specimen C-180-60-22-1.5-Fx-2

5 CONCLUSIONS

Finite Element (FE) analysis along with calculations according the Direct Strength Method (DSM) and a series of six experimental compression tests on regular cold-formed steel (CFS) C-sections and on polyurethane foam-filled C-sections were conducted to study the influence of foam on the buckling behaviour. For the investigated column section, local buckling was the controlling buckling mode in all cases. The FE beam models showed a shift from distortional buckling to local buckling in the critical failure mode, if the members were foam-filled.

Depending on the stiffness of the foam and the slenderness of the cross-section, the foam leads to higher ultimate strength of the members. The stiffer the foam, the higher is the improvement on the critical buckling stress and thus on the ultimate strength. The higher the slenderness of a member, the stronger is the positive influence of the foam. The foam is an elastic bearing of the cross-section parts normal to their plane.

At the time of the editorial deadline for these proceedings, a precise comparison of the performed tests with the predicted strength per FE analyses and DSM calculations is not possible, since the Young's modulus and the shear modulus of the used polyurethane foam were not determined yet. Material tests on the foam are scheduled in order to derive essential foam properties such as stiffness and strength. However, the improving influence of polyurethane foam on a CFS C-section is shown clearly in both the calculations and the compression tests. Due to insufficient adhesion, the performance of the foam was restraint in some tests. In the future, the use of adhesion promoter is planned in order to solve that problem.

The beam FE analyses show a strong improvement on the distortional buckling behaviour. The controlling buckling mode for the foam-filled beams were local modes, whereas distortional buckling has controlled the cross-sections without foam.

Because of the supporting behaviour of the foam, a more economical design is possible. Determination of ideal cross-section shapes becomes an optimization problem that is dependent on the acting internal forces and the material properties of CFS and the polyurethane foam.

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